

A review of the current measures used within the English courts for vulnerable individuals with autism spectrum disorder

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Published by Psychreg Ltd
ISSN: 2515-138X

Research has highlighted that individuals who are defined as vulnerable come into regular contact with the criminal justice system (Burton et al., 2006; King & Murphy, 2014). Certain vulnerabilities, such as mental disabilities, can impact how the individual is perceived within the criminal justice system (Wainwright & Mojtahedi, 2020). Moreover, these vulnerabilities could impact an individual's ability to participate fully in a trial, affecting their ability to give evidence; therefore, the use of special adaptations or measures within the criminal justice system is imperative to reduce the levels of stress experienced by a witness, while preserving the quality of the evidence they can give (Lindsey, 2019). Therefore, there must be adaptations put in place in order to facilitate a trial.

Keywords: autism spectrum disorder; court trial; criminal justice; English courts; legal psychology

The importance of using adaptations within the courts is paramount, and legal professionals have highlighted the importance of adaptations and research has suggested that lawyers and barristers who have questioned vulnerable individuals (those with a diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder) found the process difficult, concluding that the use of adaptations to be a positive experience overall (Maras et al., 2017).

Research has suggested that individuals with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) might be more likely to come into contact with the criminal justice system as either a witness or a defendant due to the characteristics associated with their diagnosis (King & Murphy, 2014). Therefore, it is important to understand what adaptations and support are in place to access a fair trial and understand their experiences with the courts.

The current commentary aims to give an overview of how the English courts define vulnerability and the current adaptations within the court. It will also look briefly at some of the research that has been conducted into their efficacy and the attitudes towards them. Finally, this summary will aim to explore the experience of individuals with ASD within the criminal justice system and highlight any gaps in the literature regarding courtroom adaptations.

Defining vulnerable individuals and the special measures available

Within the English courts, any witness under the age of 18 is automatically considered a vulnerable witness. Those over the age of 18 are defined as vulnerable if they have a diagnosed mental health disorder (as defined within the Mental Health Act 1983), a physical disability, or if they have a significant deficit with their social communication or intelligence that would significantly impair the quality of the evidence they can give (Burton et al., 2006; House of Commons, 2018; National Autistic Society, 2011). Witnesses who are considered to be at risk of intimidation from the defendant or their associates are also defined as vulnerable and can access special measures within the court (Burton et al., 2006).

Following a Home Office report 'Speaking up for Justice', which focused on the treatment of vulnerable and intimidated witnesses, a number of special measures to support vulnerable witnesses were introduced with the Youth Justice and Criminal Evidence Act, 1999 (Burton et al., 2006; Cooper & Mattison, 2017; Ellison & Munro 2014; House of Commons, 2018). These adaptations are: (a) use of screens to shield the witness from the view of the defendant; (b) technology to allow the witness to give evidence from outside the court via a live video link; (c) allowing the witness to give evidence in private (the press and public are excluded from court); (d) removal of wigs and gowns worn by legal professionals within the court; (e) using a pre-recorded video interview rather than giving evidence in person; (f) use of an intermediary to support communication between the witness and the legal professionals; (g) use of communication aids such as a communicator, interpreter, or a communication aid.

The court ultimately decides which adaptation, if any, will be used in a trial. This is taken on a case-by-case basis and is dependent on the needs of the individual (House of Commons, 2018). Within the available literature and relevant legislation, it appears that these special measures were originally intended for and are used most frequently for vulnerable witnesses and victims of crime (House of Commons, 2018). However, the courts can allow vulnerable defendants to have access to an intermediary to facilitate a fair trial if it is deemed to be needed (House of Commons, 2018). More recently, vulnerable defendants have also had access to a live video link to give their testimony (Fairclough, 2017).

In relation to individuals with ASD, there has been some sharing of knowledge and understanding for those working with individuals with ASD by the National Autistic Society (2011), and Government legislation has sought to improve the experience of individuals with ASD in the courtroom through the introduction of special measures or adaptations (House of Commons, 2018). Similarly, Allely (2015) highlighted that the Advocacy Training Council and Legal Education Foundation provided a toolkit for legal professionals to support working with an individual with ASD. However, there is a gap in the literature looking at what evidence or teaching is provided to the jury during a trial or the effectiveness of such information-sharing.

Examination of the special measures

Within the current literature, there appears to be a focus on the use of special measures for vulnerable witnesses (Ellison & Munro, 2014); however, despite the wide range of adaptations set out for use, the research focuses mainly on the witness intermediary scheme and the use of live links and pre-recorded interviews (Burrows & Powell 2014; Ellison & Munro, 2014). This may be explained by these being the most frequently used adaptations or the adaptations that have caused the most concern regarding the impact on conviction or jury decision-making.

Screens within the court

Burton et al. (2006) highlighted that screens were predominately used for vulnerable and intimidated adult witnesses rather than children. These were usually applied for the day of the trial and varied between the courtroom regarding whether the witness was obscured from the defendant during their entire time in court or just while in the witness box.

Legal professionals felt that screens often gave confidence to the witnesses who used them (Burton et al., 2006). The Crown prosecution service highlighted that judges often preferred screens over live link videos for witnesses to give evidence as they held a preference for people giving evidence in court (Burton et al., 2006).

Burton et al. (2006) also highlighted some confusion within the criminal justice system regarding who can use a screen, with many professionals reporting they felt that screens were only for use in cases where there was a victim of sexual assault or abuse rather than for witnesses with other vulnerabilities (for example intellectual disability or ASD) who could benefit from the use of a screen (Burton et al., 2006).

Live link video

A live video link uses a video link between the courtroom and another separate room where the witness can give live evidence and interact with the court without being in the courtroom (Burton et al., 2006). This measure was reported as being perceived as 'effective' or 'very effective' by legal professionals surveyed (Burton et al., 2006). This was attributed to the perceived levels of confidence and reduced levels of fear or intimidation afforded to the witnesses by not having to enter the courtroom (Burton et al., 2006). On the other hand, Burton et al. (2006) highlighted difficulty using a live link with a child witness. Within their research, the legal professionals who took part suggested that as children can sit low in relation to the camera key body language indicators, the jury may determine credibility could potentially be lost (Burton et al., 2006). Fairclough (2017) reported that a live link was accessible for use by a vulnerable defendant within the criminal justice system; however, this was reported to be used very rarely.

Pre-recorded evidence

The use of pre-recorded evidence is also referred to as evidence-in-chief and is reported to be used mainly for child witnesses (Burton et al., 2006). Several shortcomings regarding the use of evidence-in-chief have been highlighted within the literature (Burton et al., 2006). This included technical difficulties resulting in poor sound quality or video quality within the courtroom and the witness being underprepared for cross-examination resulting in concerns regarding undermining their credibility (Burton et al., 2006)

Research exploring the use of evidence-in-chief with child witness interviews in the New Zealand criminal justice system has shown similar concerns to those reported in Burton et al. (2006) (Burrows & Powell, 2014). Legal professionals felt positives about using evidence-in-chief in relation to child witnesses due to the more complete and cohesive evidence gathered compared to written statements. This research also highlighted concerns regarding technical issues with the quality of the recordings used, and it was reported that using pre-recorded interviews reduced the juror engagement with the witness compared to giving live evidence, reducing the sense of the formality of the evidence and resulted in the child witnesses being less prepared for cross-examination and often presenting as more anxious (Burrows & Powell, 2014).

Although these different measures have been described in more detail above, Ellison and Munro (2014) explored the impact of three different adaptations on verdicts of guilt. They highlighted the mixed research evidence on adults' perception of children's testimony, with some showing an impact on conviction rates and others showing no effect. Using screens, live links, and pre-recorded interviews, Ellison and Munro (2014) found no clear or consistent patterns in impact on verdicts given in a mock jury scenario. Similar findings were presented by Taylor and Joudo (2005), who found that jury perception of credibility did not differ between individuals who gave evidence in the court via live video link or video evidence.

Removal of wigs and gowns

The removal of wigs and gowns within the court was initially designed to be used for those witnesses who found the court context confusing and therefore impact their ability to testify, for example, those with an Intellectual disability or ASD (Burton et al., 2006). The use of this measure is reported to be used at the presiding judge's discretion (Burton et al., 2006).

There is limited research regarding the use of this measure; however, Burton et al. (2006) highlighted that this measure is nearly always refused when offered to child witnesses, and it has been suggested by legal professionals to be an ineffective measure. This, therefore, suggests that it is a rarely used adaptation.

Giving evidence in a closed court

Giving evidence within a closed court gives the judge the power to exclude individuals from the courtroom while a witness gives evidence (Burton et al., 2006).

There is limited research evidence regarding this measure; however, those included in Burton et al. (2006) highlighted that although there could be merits for using this measure, especially in cases of sexual assault or when intimidation is a significant issue, there were concerns that this measure could conflict with the principle of open justice (Burton et al., 2006).

Witness intermediary scheme

The witness intermediary scheme provides a registered intermediary to vulnerable witnesses. The Intermediary is a trained, impartial professional who facilitates the communication between the justice system and the vulnerable witness. It is aimed to support witnesses and victims of crime, whose quality of evidence would be adversely affected by their additional needs (Cooper & Mattison, 2017; House of Commons, 2018; Maras et al., 2017; National Autistic Society, 2011;). The role of an intermediary includes assessing an individual's communication needs and recommending specific strategies and recommendations to support the legal professionals in communicating and questioning the witness and preparing them for the various criminal justice procedures. They also recommend using appropriate communication devices, and finally, they monitor and manage associated anxiety and its impact on their ability to communicate within the court (House of Commons, 2018).

Maras et al. (2017) explored the experiences of adjustments and adaptations in court. They found that over half of the legal professionals responded that the witness intermediary scheme was helpful; however, only a third of solicitors and barristers and half of the judges felt comfortable working with an intermediary (Maras et al., 2017). Despite there being some research into the use of intermediaries, Cooper and Mattison (2017) highlighted a lack of empirical research that impacts the ability to evaluate the role fully.

Liaison and diversion

In England and Wales, liaison and diversion services have been developed to support individuals present within the criminal justice system with suspected vulnerabilities (Chaplin et al., 2017). Once an individual has arrived at court, they would often be assessed by a Liaison and Diversion team (Chaplin et al., 2017). As part of this assessment, the Liaison and Diversion team will often provide a pre-sentencing report to support risk management and a detailed sentence plan.

Other adaptations

Although not an adaptation set out in legislation, Maras et al. (2017) noted that strategies, such as pre-court visits, practice interviews, detailed explanations, and clear communication, were all highlighted as helpful to those with ASD. In contrast, a lack of these, especially regarding communication, caused more distress.

The experience of individuals with autism spectrum disorder within the court

There is a limited amount of research that aims to explore the experience of individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder in the criminal justice system (Chaplin et al., 2017; Helverschou et al., 2018); research has been more focused on looking at the prevalence and exploring the characteristics that can impact on their offending behaviour (Freckelton 2013; King & Murphy 2004). Allen et al. (2008) highlighted that due to the vulnerabilities associated with ASD, individuals with a diagnosis often struggle to navigate the criminal justice system, suggesting that research focusing on additional support and adaptations is vital.

Individuals with ASD who had the experience of the criminal justice system reported that very few were offered adaptations during their appearances in court (25% screens, 11% give evidence via video link, 7% removal of wigs and gowns). (Maras et al., 2017). Likewise, both individuals with ASD and parents of children with ASD who had experienced court reported that there were a number of challenges, the most common was the lack of proper understanding from the legal professionals regarding ASD, especially regarding understanding the difficulties individuals with ASD face when trying to give a narrative account and difficulties

with remembering (Maras et al., 2017). Similar reports were found by Burton et al. (2007), who reported that many witnesses were not provided with the support they felt would help them.

Despite research highlighting that legal professionals reported satisfaction with their encounters with individuals with ASD in a professional context, less than a fifth of those within the autism community reported satisfaction with their dealings with the criminal justice system (Maras et al., 2017). Therefore, this suggests that despite access to adaptations, these are not perceived as a positive experience for those classed as vulnerable. However, it is worth noting that the limited access to adaptations could have resulted in individuals' low satisfaction; therefore, further research into this is needed.

As with most of the empirical research looking at the impact of special measures or the experience of vulnerable individuals in the criminal justice system, most of the research has focused on vulnerable witnesses. Helverschou et al. (2018) interviewed a small number of offenders with ASD to understand their experience of their arrest, trial, and time in prison. The participants reported that although they had access to a defence lawyer, they often felt that their case had not been fully represented (Helverschou et al., 2018). Participants also described mixed experiences of understanding the trial, with some stating that although they understood what was going on, they felt that they had not had enough time to explain their behaviour. The others reported that the trial was stressful and challenging (Helverschou et al., 2018). One participant explained that the expectation they spoke was more challenging for them as they express themselves better through writing (Helverschou et al., 2018). Helverschou et al. (2018) also highlighted that individuals with ASD remained confused throughout the process, and none felt that their lawyer truly understood them.

Although there is the option for vulnerable defendants to give their testimony through a live link, this is rarely taken up (Fairclough, 2017). This could have an adverse effect on the defendant to give evidence poorly through lack of support, which in turn could influence the jury decision (Fairclough, 2017). This research highlighted a lack of knowledge from legal professionals that vulnerable defendants could meet the criteria to use a live link, therefore suggesting that further education is needed to ensure vulnerable defendants with ASD have access to adequate adaptations (Fairclough 2017).

Browning and Caulfield (2011) highlighted the lack of training and understanding of legal professionals working with those with an ASD diagnosis. This impacts an individual's experience within the criminal justice system and could have a negative impact on the outcome of their trial. Browning and Caulfield (2011) propose that this negative experience can be reduced somewhat with access to a legal team with adequate knowledge or an appropriate adult.

Evaluations of the special measures currently used within the courts further highlighted that legal professionals were either unaware that certain adaptations could be used with individuals with ASD (screens) or put little merit in the adaptations that could be most beneficial to individuals with ASD (removal of wigs and gowns) (Burton et al., 2006). This, therefore, suggests that individuals with ASD could not be getting access to necessary adaptations that could help them within a court setting.

Directions for future research and investigation

Research has shown that vulnerable witnesses can provide reliable and accurate evidence when the correct provisions are put in place (Gibert & Mojtahedi, 2019), highlighting the importance of research into improving the adaptations put in place for vulnerable individuals within forensic and legal settings. The literature on adaptations in court focuses on their use with vulnerable witnesses (Burton et al., 2006; Ellison & Munro, 2014). There appears to be a gap within the literature looking at their use with vulnerable defendants. Although the guidance focuses on their use with vulnerable witnesses, there is guidance that some adaptations can be used with vulnerable defendants at the discretion of the court (House of Commons, 2018). Within the European Convention on Human Rights, a defendant is entitled to "informed promptly and in detail, in a language which the defendant understands, of the nature and cause of the accusation that has been made"; however it is still commonplace that vulnerable defendants do not have adequate access to appropriate special measures, (Chaplin et al., 2017). This is also highlighted by Hoyano (2015), who reported that a vulnerable defendant should have access to the same special measures as vulnerable witnesses.

A systemic review undertaken by King and Murphy (2014) suggested that the prevalence of ASD within an offending population varied between 3 and 27%, which is significantly higher than the prevalence rate found within the general population. Freckelton (2013) highlighted the increase in requests for professional reports to be provided to the courts and jury for individuals with ASD who have been convicted of a criminal offence. This would suggest that there is an increasing need to provide an understanding for the criminal justice system regarding vulnerabilities a defendant has in order to contextualise their behaviour or provide relevant

additional information. Therefore, it could be argued that if a professional understanding is needed for the court, the defendants with a vulnerability could present in a way that would make it beneficial for them to have access to adaptations to facilitate their participation in the trial. However, there is currently a gap in the research exploring this.

It appears that within the currently available literature, the focus has been on an adult's perception of children's testimony (Burrows & Powell 2014). This could be because all children who are witnesses or victims are automatically considered vulnerable and have access to a range of special measures, whereas adults have to apply and prove that they fall within a defined category (Burton et al., 2006). Therefore, there is a lack of evidence of perceptions of adults who use special measures in the court and whether this impacts on verdicts given or jury decision making.

Despite a growing body of research into the impact of using special measures within the criminal justice system, Lindsay (2019) highlighted that there is still a need for further research into the perception of using special measures. Especially on jury decision-making and verdicts.

CONCLUSION

There is clear legislation and guidance regarding the need for appropriate adaptations for individuals who are considered vulnerable witnesses (Burton et al., 2006; House of Commons, 2018). However, this appears to be lacking for defendants who have similar vulnerabilities (Fairclough, 2017). Although there is some evidence exploring the impact of these, it is clear that more is needed to fully understand the effectiveness or impact of using these in a trial scenario. This brief overview has highlighted some of the experiences that individuals with ASD could experience when involved with the criminal justice system; however, it has also highlighted the lack of research focused on this area. Further research is needed to fully understand the experience of individuals with ASD in the courts and the impact of any special adaptations or measures afforded to them.

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